

Foreign-language pharmacophytonyms in the oral discourse of the Bashkirs (based on the database of the Machine Fund of the Bashkir language)

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Article History

Received: 12.09.2024

Accepted: 17.10.2024

Published: 10.11.2024

Abstract: The article considers the functioning of foreign-language pharmacophytonyms in the Bashkir language. The material for the study is dictionaries, as well as materials from the database of the Machine Fund of the Bashkir language (hereinafter referred to as the MFBL) and the oral subcorpus of the Bashkir language mass media, developed by the staff of the Laboratory of Linguistics and Information Technologies (now the Department of Applied Linguistics and Dialectology) of the Institute of History, Language and Literature of the Ufa Federal Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The information system of the Machine Fund of the Bashkir language consists of 7 large databases, which form sub-funds of a single fund: sub-fund of the general card index; lexicographic sub-fund; grammatical sub-fund; sub-fund of the catalog of handwritten books; sub-fund of the catalog of early printed books; experimental-phonetic sub-fund; dialectological sub-fund and 3 corpus projects: a corpus of prose, a corpus of journalism and a corpus of folklore. The object of the study was foreign names of medicinal plants in the Bashkir language. The purpose of this article is to describe the borrowed words that are included in the pharmacophytonyms in the Bashkir language. The availability of wide access to dialect materials is a factor in preserving the native language in the context of globalization of modern society.

Keywords: Bashkir language, pharmacophytonyms, foreign words, machine fund of the Bashkir language, database, plant vocabulary, dialectological base.

Cite this article:

Shaukatovna, I. A., Aisovna, B. L., (2024). Foreign-language pharmacophytonyms in the oral discourse of the Bashkirs (based on the database of the Machine Fund of the Bashkir language). *ISAR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(11), 20-25.

Introduction

The use of corpora is a useful tool for language research, as it allows studying the language in a broader context. Corpora provide access to larger volumes of text, which provides more data for language study. In addition, the use of corpora can help in the analysis of various aspects of the language, such as phrases, sentence structure, the use of certain words, and grammatical constructions. Therefore, the use of corpora has found application in modern research practice and has become an important achievement of linguistic science.

Developed by the Laboratory of Linguistics and Information Technologies (now the Department of Applied Linguistics and Dialectology) of the Institute of History, Language and Literature of the Ufa Federal Research Center of the Russian Academy of

Sciences, the Machine Fund of the Bashkir Language (hereinafter referred to as the MFBL) is a repository of almost the entire lexical wealth of the Bashkir language. This information system currently includes 7 large databases:

- general card index,
- lexicographic database,
- grammar database,
- catalog of handwritten books,
- catalog of early printed books,
- experimental phonetic database,
- dialectological database

and 3 corpus projects:

– corpus of prose texts,

– corpus of journalism,

– corpus of folklore texts (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Interface of the Machine Fund of the Bashkir language: mfb12.ru

Material, Methods

The dialectological database consists of three independent databases: lexical (information on more than 52 thousand dialect units with six information fields: the dialect word itself, part of speech, dialect, speech, literary norm, Russian translation), cartographic (information on the dialectological atlas of the Bashkir language - phonetic, morphological, syntactic, lexical linguistic features), textual (samples of oral speech) [Sirazitdinov, 2020, p. 76] (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Interface of the MFBL Dialectological base

The lexical database contains more than 52,000 dialect units, consisting of 9 information fields: dialect word, part of speech, dialect, speech, literary norm, Russian translation, example of use, additional information, set expressions.

Fig. 3. Example of searching and displaying the lexeme ‘cucumber’

In the Kyzyl, Miass, and Salut subdialects of the eastern dialect, and in the middle subdialect of the southern dialect, there are borrowed words from ‘cucumber’ *әәһрә* / *әәһрә* / *үһерә* / *әәһрә* [MFBL: Dialectological base]. The Dictionary of Early Russian Borrowings notes that the source of this lexeme is the Greek ‘immature’ [Dictionary of Early Russian Borrowings of the Bashkir Language, 2021, p. 236]. According to the opinions of A.G. Biyshev and E.F. Ishberdin, the literary name *kyar* is borrowed from the Arabic language *كبر* as ‘one of the types of vegetables, cucumber’ [Biyshev, 2009, p. 63; Ishberdin, 2002, p. 65]. The dialectological atlas database contains information on the dialectological atlas of the Bashkir language, which contains rich dialectal material from the strongholds of the Republic of Bashkortostan and neighboring regions where the Bashkir population lives compactly (Kurgan, Orenburg, Perm, Samara, Saratov, Sverdlovsk, Chelyabinsk regions).

The database interface includes the following features:

1) Selection of the language match type: phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic.

2) Selection of the language match subtype (for example, for phonetic matches: by sonants and consonants).

3) Selection of a specific language match (in the form of a specific opposition of linguistic phenomena in different positions in words and constructions).

It should be noted that the popular names of plants differ in the degree of their prevalence and dialect affiliation. At the same time, in the same dialects, two or three, and sometimes more, synonymous names are often used [Ishmukhametova, 2021, p. 82]. In the lexical section of the dialectological database, the program gives us more than 50 synonymous variants of the lexeme hawthorn: *айыу камыр*, *байарка*, *баяр емеше*, *без агасы*, *бөгән*; *дөгәнәк йемеше*, *дунала*, *езагас*, *езем*, *езәй*, *емшегән*, *йезе*, *йәбеишкән*, *йәһәр*, *йөзөм*, *йушан*, *камыр жыләге*, *камырийемеш*, *камырлама*, *камырлауык*, *камырлык*, *кара кайын*, *мәмешкәк*, *һыһар*, *тештекәй*, *типкечле агач*, *төлкөйемеш агасы*, *төлкөйемеш*, *энагас*, *энаде*, *энадек*, *энайемеше*, *энәлек*, *энәлекәй*, *энтаештегайын*, *энтаештекәй*, *энтәкес*, *эт емеше*, *әбей йемеше*, etc. [MFBL: Dialectological base].

Fig. 4. Map with isoglosses of the name of hawthorn

The dialectological atlas database contains a lexical isogloss of the name of hawthorn (Fig. 4).

It should be noted that in a number of Turkic languages the following phonetic variants of this lexeme are found in the same meaning: *dolana* Kaz., *dolono* Kirg., *dülana* Uz., *doluna* Uygh., *dülänä* Tat. dialect., *tolono* Alt., *dolagana* Tuv., *dolayana* Tof., *doloqono* / *doloquna* Yak.; as a result of metathesis – Bashk. *dumala*. The lexeme **dolayana* is of Mongolian origin, cf. P.-Mong. *dolyana* ~ *dolunu*, Mong. *dolo:gono*, Kalm. *dolaŋk* [SIGTYA, 1997, p. 124]. M. Räsänen traces the forms *dolayana* and *dola:na* he cites to Mongolian *dolayana* [Räsänen, 1969, p. 139]. As a result of metathesis, the lexeme *dunala* is found in the Bashkir language. The textual database of the MFBL contains examples of colloquial speech in Bashkir dialects. The presence of meta-information indicating:

- 1) The informant's gender (male, female),
- 2) Place of residence,
- 3) Age (0-11, 12-15, 16-25, 26-45, 46-65, 66 and above),
- 4) Level of education (primary, secondary, university),
- 5) Language of communication in the family (Bashkir, Russian, Tatar),
- 6) Nationality will be of great importance for conducting various sociological studies.

The following 15 topics were defined for recording informants:

- Wedding, wedding customs;
- Food (everyday and festive);
- Domestic animals (what kind and how they are kept);
- Kinship system (children and close relatives);
- Household plot (vegetable garden, orchard);
- House, buildings (when and by whom it was built, what kind of roof, frames);
- Toponymy in the vicinity of the settlement;
- History of the village, clan, school;
- Everyday life (work, school);
- Seasons, weather;
- Small forms of folklore (ditties, proverbs, sayings, fairy tales);
- Trip to the district center (for what purpose, what kind of transport is used);
- Children's games;
- Friends;
- Animal and plant life near the settlement (what birds and animals live there) (Fig. 5) [Sirazitdinov et al., 2018, p. 101].

Fig. 5. Example of output of transcription texts of speech of representatives of females with secondary education aged 26-45 years

The database interface allows searching for texts by many linguistic and extralinguistic parameters: dialect, speech, year of recording, informant's education, gender, age, nationality.

Results and Discussion

Russian-language pharmacophytonyms in the database of the Machine Fund of the Bashkir language

The Russian language has had a huge influence on the Bashkir language, especially in the sphere of vocabulary and grammar. Borrowings from the Russian language occurred both directly and

through the Russian language. As K.Z. Zakiryaynov states, "in the conditions of contact between the Russian and Bashkir languages, the influence of the Russian language on Bashkir turned out to be the strongest, which can be explained as follows. In the process of contact, a language with broader social functions usually has a greater influence on a language with a narrower sphere of functional use. So it is in this case: the Russian language as a language with broader social functions made a greater contribution to the development of the Bashkir language" [Zakiryaynov, 2002, p. 96]. In diachronic terms, T.M. Garipov divides Russian borrowings into two fundamentally different periods: pre-revolutionary and

post-revolutionary, differing from each other both in the nature of the borrowings and in their design on Bashkir soil.

Before the revolution, mainly household and everyday terminology was borrowed, which was subjected to significant sound processing in accordance with the pronunciation norms of the Bashkir language. This includes the names of the following pharmacophytonyms: lit. *арыш* 'rye', dial. *пирэй* (Democratic speaking southern dialect) lit. *актамыр* 'wheatgrass', dial. *сәснүк* / *сәснөк* (Sakmar speaking southern dialect) lit. *һарымһаҡ* 'garlic' lit. *картуф* 'potato', dial. *шарфый* (Middle Southern Dialectical) / *шалфей* (Kyzyl Eastern Dialectical) 'sage', *маркуф* (Middle Southern Dialectical) 'carrot', etc. [MFBL: Dialectological base] These borrowings have been modified according to the structural features of the language. All early borrowings from Russian have undergone such a change, since during this period Russian words penetrated into the Bashkir language mainly through the spoken language. An analysis of pharmacophytonyms shows that later borrowings are used without changes: parsley, calendula, chrysanthemum, etc. This is evidenced by materials that were included in the oral subcorpus of the Bashkir language media: [*рәтифә буранбаева*] *гәлийемеш* / # *календула* # / # *чабрец* # / # *малина* # / *кара карагат һәм еләк япрактарында* / *балтыргандың һабагында һәм япрактарында* / *с витамини күп* // '[Ratifa Buranbaeva] in rose hips / calendula / thyme / raspberries / black currants and on the leaves of the berry / on the stem and leaves of hogweed / a lot of vitamin c' [MFBL: Textological base].

It should also be especially noted that most Russian-language names of medicinal plants are borrowed from the Latin language, since the botanical nomenclature was created on a Greco-Latin basis. bash. *календула* ← rus. *calendula* ← lat. *Calendula*, bash. *цикорий* ← rus. *chicory* ← lat. *Cichórium*, bash. *примула* ← rus. *primrose* ← lat. *Primula*, bash. *әнис* ← rus. *anise* ← lat. *Anisum*, bash. *тимьян* ← rus. *thyme* ← lat. *Thýmus* ← ancient Greek *θύμος*, bash. *мелисса* ← rus. *melissa* ← lat. *Melissa*, bash. *алоэ* / *алой* ← Russian: *aloe* ← Latin: *Áloë* etc.

Яран 'geranium' Lat. *Geranium* – belongs to the geranium family lat. *Geraniaceae* Juss. The Russian-Bashkir dictionary mentions several varieties of this plant: *та'* [RBS, 2005, p. 229]. The following dialectal variants of this flower are recorded in the Middle Ural dialect of the Eastern dialect: one Maryamana, and in that same speech blood-red geranium - *алмайара* (dex. apple+rana) [MFBL: Dialectological base] Geranium, which is grown at home, is called *ярангөл* (def. geranium+flower). It is a plant having antiseptic, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-emetic, wound healing and other properties. activities, noted in newspaper texts of the Publicity Corps of the MFBL. Cf: *Арыганда, депрессиянан, баш ауыртканда ярангөлдө ескәргә кәрәк* 'When tired, depressed, headache should smell yarangul' [MFBL: Journalism Corps] – 'When tired, depressed, headache, you should breathe the aroma of geranium'.

Russian-language words are also found in the Textual Database of the MFBL. Initially, this database was created to present illustrative material on dialects based on the "Samples of Bashkir Colloquial Speech" [Samples... 1988], but later the database was filled with transcriptions of phonetic speech in dialects of the eastern dialect, collected and transcribed as part of the laboratory's research project "Creation of a Corpus of Dialectal Texts of the Bashkir Language" (2017-2021). In the process of speech,

informants were observed to use foreign-language words, i.e. "code switching - the speaker's transition in the process of speech communication from one language to another depending on the communication conditions" [Baganova et al., 2010, p. 64], in this case, the use of Russian terms in Bashkir speech. During the conversation, the informant uses the Russian name of plants, thus code switching occurs. Wed: # *гваздикалар* # # *шуттан* # *бөткөһөз* / *сәскәләрем нык күп* // лит. *кәнәферзәр һанан бөткөһөз / сәскәләрем нык күп* // 'гвоздик не сосчитать / у меня очень много цветов //' (f., 48, secondary, Kyzyl) ; # *и* # *әсәйзен йараткан сәскәләр* # *роза* # *гартензийалар үсә* // лит. *һәм әсәйзең яраткан сәскәләре рауза гортензиялар үсә* // 'and mother's favorite flowers, hydrangea roses, are growing' // (f., 14, secondary, Kyzyl) [MFBL: Textological base]. In the above examples, code switching from Bashkir to Russian is motivated by the fact that during the communication process, for some reason, the informant cannot remember the right word in his native language and switches to Russian.

Segmentation and transcription of oral material is carried out in the ELAN annotation program.

The following signs were used as special transcription signs:

(..) — a sign of a long pause in the informant's speech flow;

() — a sign of a hesitation pause, if it is filled with some sounds, the corresponding letter symbols are placed inside brackets: for example, eh (eh-eh);

(//) — a break in the utterance before the next word;

[] — self-correction (an incorrect word or grammatical form, which are subsequently corrected by the informant);

.. — a break in the word before the next word;

\$ C — a paralinguistic element of speech — laughter;

\$ K — a paralinguistic element of speech — cough;

\$ B — a paralinguistic element of speech — a sigh, a groan, smacking of the lips, etc.

... # — switching language codes (from Bashkir to Russian).

In the Textological Base, the code switch on both sides is marked with the symbol octothorp (#) to distinguish them from originally Bashkir words and borrowings that have become fixed in the lexical system of Bashkir2 19]. During the conversation the informant uses the Russian name of the plant, i.e. code switching occurs. Cf: *кырза үскән () курай йеләге лә тәмде* / # *малина* # // лит. *кырза үскән курай еләге лә тәмде / курай еләге* // 'and forest raspberry is delicious / raspberry //' (51, zh., middle, uchalsky); (мм) *теге # малина # нимәкәй +булалә* / # *малина* #? *әб*ерсә үсә* // лит. *теге малина нимәкәй була әлә / малина? курай еләге үсә* // 'what is the name of a raspberry? raspberry grows //' (40, f., medium, Kyzylsky) [MFBL: Dialectological base].

In the above examples, the code switch from Bashkir to Russian is motivated by the fact that during communication for some reason the informant cannot remember the necessary word in his native language and switches to Russian.

Conclusions

In recent years, the use of traditional medicine has become more active, and herbal treatment is gaining popularity. Humanity increasingly prefers natural food, including medicinal herbs.

Information is viewed in newspapers, magazines, and collected in social networks. Health programs broadcast on radio and television are also a source of information.

One of the features of the use of pharmacophytonymic nomenclature in the speech of the Bashkirs is that the names of plants and their medicinal properties are preserved in the people's memory and this knowledge is passed down from generation to generation. Pharmacophytonyms are becoming an integral part of the speech of the Bashkirs and contribute to the preservation of traditional methods of treatment.

The machine fund of the Bashkir language is an important object of research for linguists and language scholars. The study of its features allows us to more deeply understand and describe the linguistic picture of the world of the Bashkir people, and also contributes to the preservation and development of the Bashkir language in the modern multilingual reality.

Acknowledgements: The research was supported by the Russian Science Foundation (project No. 23-28-01343 'Bashkir-Russian code-switching (based on dialect discourses)' (<https://rscf.ru/project/23-28-01343/>).

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